

Relative mtDNA Copy Number qPCR Assay

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In general:

- We use the BioRad qPCR CFX96 Real Time PCR Machine from the DNA Sequencing Facility in Barker Hall
- To Access the Machine: contact dnaseq@berkeley.edu. You need to reserve your time on the calendar they provide
- To get key card access to Barker Hall, contact Greg Vitan (vitan@berkeley.edu) and provide them the serial number on the back of your Cal1 Card
- Next, the room for the qPCR machine is located in Barker Hall room 234
 - The code to enter the room is (Press 3 & 4 at the same time and then press 5)
- Log-in to the computer and open Biorad CFX manager. Password for the Lewis Lab is 789012

C. elegans Relative mtDNA Copy Number From Crude Lysates

Protocol is adapted from

Rooney, John P et al. "PCR based determination of mitochondrial DNA copy number in multiple species." *Methods in molecular biology* (Clifton, N.J.) vol. 1241 (2015): 23–38. doi:10.1007/978-1-4939-1875-1_3

Primers for *C. elegans* based copy number determination are also taken from the above publication.

OSL10/11 amplify a 75 bp amplicon of ND1 of mtDNA in *C. elegans*

OSL 19/20 amplify a 164 bp amplicon of COX4 of Nuclear DNA in *C. elegans*

*the primers tend to have a propensity to form primer dimers so please make a 10 uM aliquot of the stock primers. Please consult the "qPCR Plate Setup and Running" protocol for more information

Materials Required:

- Thermo Scientific™ PCR Plate, 96-well, low profile, non-skirted (AB700W)
- SsoAdvanced™ Universal SYBR Green Supermix, 500 x 20 ul rxns, 5 ml (5 x 1 ml) (1725271)
- Filter/Barrier Tips
- 10X PCR Buffer (Recipe at the end)
- DEPEC Treated Nuclease Free Water
- mtDNA Primers (OSL 10/11)
- NuclearDNA Primers (OSL 19/20)

- Alkaline Bleach Solution/ Spot Bleach Solution (Recipe Below)
- 20°C Incubators
- Single 0.2 ml PCR tubes
- Film, Sealing, Thermo Scientific, ABSolute qPCR Seal, Microplate, Adhesive, qPCR and Storage, RNase/DNase/Endotoxin Free, -80 deg. C to 110 deg. C, 50 Sheets, (AB1170)
- Proteinase K (20mg/ml) Aliquot

Recipes:

Proteinase K (20 mg/ml)

Component	Amount	
Proteinase K	0.04 g	
Millipore H2O*	2 mL	(use p1000 pipette)

- 1) Filter sterilize using a 0.2µm filter and syringe.
- 2) Store 100ul aliquots at -20°C

SPOT BLEACHING/Alkaline Bleach Solution

Component	Amount
Sterile MiliQ Water	3.75 ml
5N NaOH	500 ul
Sodium Hypochlorite(Bleach)	1 ml
TOTAL	5 ml

ALWAYS MAKE FRESH ON DAY OF BLEACHING

10X PCR Buffer For Single Worm Lysis

Component	Amount
1M Tris pH 8.0	1 ml
1M KCl	5 ml
1M MgCl ₂	200 ul
H ₂ O	3.8 ml
TOTAL	10 ml

A note on Biological Replicates:

- To make the most sense of your data and ensure rigor, here is how Dr. Lewis and Nitin defined a biological replicate for these experiments
 - A biological replicate will include worms bleached on the same day. To get different biological replicates, **YOU MUST BLEACH WORMS ON DIFFERENT DAYS**
 - A **MINIMUM** of 3 Biological replicates is required. However, anticipate making 6 biological replicates if the variation in your data is a lot. In my hands, the data makes the most sense with 6 biological replicates.

Synchronizing Worms (Small Scale):

- Three days before you want to synchronize worms, chunk worms of your desired genotypes on Spotted NGM Plates. Please use NGM plates all in the same box to control for OP50
- The worms will become gravid in about 3 days.
- On the day of bleaching, make a fresh Alkaline Bleach Solution (always make it fresh)
- When you finally have gravid adults, take a fresh NGM plate and add 50 ul of the Alkaline Bleaching Solution on the Agar portion of the NGM plate. Avoid adding the solution on the OP50 lawn.
- Quickly, pick 10-20 gravid worms into the 50 ul drop. The worms should begin to stiffen in about a few seconds. Let the worms sit in the bleach drop until fully dissolved and you can see their eggs left behind. You may have to add a second 50 ul drop onto the worms if they have not dissolved.
- Move the plates to the 20°C incubator or your desired rearing temperature
- The bleach will soak into the agar and the worms will hatch and crawl into the OP50 lawn
- Once worms reach adulthood, I transfer them to new spotted NGM plates. Keep transferring Adult worms every two days until you have the aged worms of your desire

From this small scale bleaching, I have typically yielded around 20–35 animals and that is sufficient for the crude lysate protocol and for aging experiments.

In case you need to plan your experiment evaluating copy number at different development stages, here is a helpful guide (egg laying begins = 0 day adult):

DEVELOPMENT AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES			
	"16°C" (16.0 ± 0.3°C)	"20°C" (19.5 ± 0.5°C)	"25°C" (25.0 ± 0.2°C)
Egg laid	0 hr	0 hr	0 hr
Egg hatches	16-18 hr	10-12 hr	8-9 hr
First-molt lethargus	36.5 hr	26 hr	18.0 hr
Second-molt lethargus	48 hr	34.5 hr	25.5 hr
Third-molt lethargus	60.0 hr	43.5 hr	31 hr
Fourth-molt lethargus	75 hr	56 hr	39 hr
Egg-laying begins	-90 hr	-65 hr	-47 hr
Egg-laying maximal	-140 hr	-96 hr	-62 hr
Egg-laying ends	-180 hr	-128 hr	-88 hr

(image from WormBook)

- In my hands, I typically see late L4 and Adults 72 hours after bleaching the gravid worms.

Lysing Worms:

- When you are ready to lyse worms: assemble the following lysis mixture (you may make a [copy of this spreadsheet](#) for your own use if you want)
- The ratio of worm to lysis is 1 worm to 15 ul. You may scale up or down the lysis mastermix according to your needs.

Component	1 Reaction
10X PCR Bufer	7.5
ProK	1.875
DEPEC H20	65.625
TOTAL	75

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- Using Filter Tips, pipet 75 ul of the lysis solution into the single PCR tube
- Then, pick 5 worms off the OP50 and onto a blank NGM plate/portion of your plate with no OP50 so that you minimize the amount of bacteria you pick up
- Then, pick the worms into the lysis solution.
- Spin the worms down using the PCR tube spinner
- Freeze the worms in a -80 for at least 25 minutes. You can keep worms in the the -80 for a long time (useful if you are trying to do a matched age course experiment as you can freeze younger worms from the same plate days before you get the older worms from the same plate)
- Then, use the lab's PCR machines and run the Worm Lysis Protocol on the machine. Here is the Protocol for Reference:

Temperature (C)	Time
60	60 minutes
95	15 minutes
10	Hold

- After the lysis is complete, mix the tubes using a pipette to homogenize. Pipet up and down for about 15 times and then spin the tubes down again using the PCR tube spinner

qPCR Plate Setup and Running The Round:

- Prior to making the mastermix, make a 10uM aliquot of the mtDNA Primers (OSL10/11) and Nuclear DNA Primers (OSL19/20)
- Then, assemble the following qPCR master mix (you may make a [copy of this spreadsheet](#) for your own use if you want. On the second tab, you can use the plate mockup). Add 18 ul of master mix to each well. **Please note the reaction is not multiplexed so you need to add mtDNA qPCR mastermix separately to a well and have the nuclear DNA qPCR reaction added to a different well.**
 - Also, Sam and John recommended to avoid wells that are on the border of the plate as that can cause inaccurate plate readings

Component	Stock Concentration	Target Concentration	Volume (ul)	Reactions (60)
F Primer	10uM	0.1uM	0.2	12
R Primer	10uM	0.1uM	0.2	12
Nuclease Free Water			7.6	456
SYBR Green MasterMix	2X		10	600
		TOTAL	20	
		Add 2ul of lysate for each reaction		

- It is imperative that for each biological replicate you run 3 technical replicates on the same same plate. This means for each tube of worm lysate, you need to have 3 qPCR reactions on the same plate.
- After dispensing master mix to PCR plates Seal the plate using the adhesive optical film
- Then run the following protocol:

Protocol

- 1: 50.0°C for 2:00
- 2: 95.0°C for 10:00
- 3: 95.0°C for 0:15
- 4: 60.0°C for 1:00
Plate Read
- 5: GOTO 3, 40 more times
- 6: Melt Curve 65.0°C to 95.0°C: Increment 0.5°C 0:05
Plate Read

ANALYSIS

There are several different ways you could go about analyzing your data:

a) Normalizing to Controls (DeltaDeltaCt)

- i) For each run, Average the mtDNA Ct values and then average your nuclear Ct Values. Please redo your run if you have the technical replicates varying by 1 Ct or more.
- ii) $\Delta Ct = \text{Average Nuclear Signal} - \text{Average mtDNA signal}$. Do this for each of the biological replicates as well.
- iii) Then, in a spreadsheet organize your data as follows where you list the ΔCt values for all genotypes and biological replicates

Genotype	Bio Rep1	Bio Rep2	Bio Rep3
N2 (WT)	5.02541 5074	4.09008 6604	4.61363 8025
WSL5 (Endogenously Tagged)	4.14882 7061	4.50742 5431	4.13928 4621

- iv) Average your ΔCt values for your Wildtype sample (in this example, assume the average is 4.576379901)
- v) Then, compute the DeltaDeltaCt by subtracting the value from iv) from each cell in the spreadsheet.
 - 1) Eg:

Genotype	Bio Rep1	Bio Rep2	Bio Rep3
N2 (WT)	5.025415074-4.576379901	4.090086604-4.576379901	4.613638025-4.576379901
WSL5 (Endogenously Tagged)	4.148827061-4.576379901	4.507425431-4.576379901	4.139284621-4.576379901

- 2) To compute the fold change, now for each cell, do the following operation:
 - (a) $2^{(\Delta\Delta Ct)}$

b) Obtaining relative mtDNA copies per diploid genome:

- i) You can do the following math:
 - 1) $2 * 2^{\Delta Ct}$